

Report on Final taxonomy linking channels of dissemination and Altmetrics

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Abbreviations

ALM- Article Level Metrics

CA – Consortium Agreement

DoA – Description of Action

DoW – Description of Work

EC – European Commission

GA – Grant Agreement

KoM – Kick-off Meeting

OSF – Open Science Framework

PM – Project Manager

PloS – Public Library of science

PMB – Project Management Board

Q – Question Battery

WP – Work Package

WPL – Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

This report aims to provide a taxonomy that links innovative channels of dissemination with alternative or open metrics. The taxonomy provides orientation for scholars who intend to communicate their results. The taxonomy is also useful for scholars who want to assess or reflect about their usage of innovative dissemination channels.

In order to construct the categories and dimensions for the taxonomy, we gathered information from different sources.

Firstly, we executed a review of the literature in order to provide information about the perception of scholarly relevance of innovative dissemination channels and Altmetrics.

Secondly, in order to find out how different channels of dissemination and Altmetrics are perceived among the scholarly community, we used a survey conducted within OpenUp.

Thirdly, in order to validate our results, we conducted interviews with experts in the field.

This information has been discussed with stakeholders from universities, libraries, publishers and policy makers and was finally integrated in a taxonomy where each channel of dissemination is linked to specific information about its technical characteristics, appreciation, and field specificity.

Main Results:

- Traditional channels of dissemination such as publications and conference presentations are still perceived as most relevant for the communication of results by scholars.
- There are field specific differences both in usage of innovative dissemination channels and their usage. Therefore, field specific interpretations and usages of metrics are needed.
- The taxonomy shows that there is a close relationship between scholarly appreciation and altmetrics coverage. Most of the channels that have been mentioned as relevant in the survey or the review have been integrated in a metric.
- Technical characteristics and lack of accessibility (e.g., existence of APIs) of innovative dissemination constrain usage and impede construction of metrics.
- More efforts are needed to make metrics more meaningful: contextualised presentation of data will provide more information for scholars, funders, and policy makers.

Summary

This report aims to provide a taxonomy that links innovative channels of dissemination with alternative or open metrics. The taxonomy provides orientation for scholars who intend to make use of these channels. The taxonomy is also useful for scholars who want/need? to assess or reflect about their usage. Based on the considerations of the sociology of valuation, we came up with different dimensions that constitute relevant dimensions, e.g., discourses, cultural (field specific) practices, and metrics. We provide the following approach to translate and enrich these theoretical concepts with empirical analysis conducted within OpenUp.

Firstly, to reconstruct dominant narratives and discourses, we build a review of scholarly literature about Altmetrics and innovative dissemination channels, relating to Deliverables 4.1. and 5.1., respectively.

Secondly, to map perceptions and public of these channels and Altmetrics indicators, we draw on the survey conducted within OpenUp that has been designed by all project participants coordinated and implemented by the PM. These data allow specifying general structures and field specific information.

Thirdly, these data have been validated by explorative interviews with experts in the field to reconstruct dominant interpretive patterns.

Finally, this information will be synthesized and discussed with interested communities to further deepen the resulting taxonomy. We provided preliminary results that allowed for some specification of these dimensions.

After all the empirical analysis and interpretation, we will provide a taxonomy where each channel of dissemination is linked to specific information about its potential to attract attention, appreciation within academia, field specificity, and relation to scholarly discourse. An overview of the outcome is provided in chapter 4.

1. Introduction

This report provides orientation for scholars who intend to make use of innovative types of dissemination channels or are about to critically assess or reflect about their usage. In a previous report, we have put forward the idea that different channels of scholarly dissemination are attributed value in various practices of usage, appreciation, and measurement (Deliverable 5.1.).¹ Based on ‘acts of valuation’, these different channels have a certain medium-inherent value. That is, worth which is derived by the specific function it seeks to provide, beside dissemination, such as entertaining, organizing attribution and so on. In addition, these medium-based value attributions of channels of dissemination are valorised through classifications, indicators, scholarly debates, and cultures of appreciation in their disciplines.

Our goal is to develop a taxonomy of different channels of dissemination which are linked to various dimensions of appreciation and evaluation. The taxonomy is both derived from theoretical considerations based on the sociology of valuation, as well as empirically grounded. We provide dimensions of appreciation based on scholarly debates. We also present context specific characteristics of these dimensions by relating them to factors such as age or academic discipline. Scholars are provided resources to critically assess whether the dissemination channels are suitable for and appreciated by the audience they intend to reach. Since new metrics of research communication output increasingly influence scholarly practices we will also provide an overview of how dissemination is measured by different providers and data services.

The report is structured as follows: In the following section (chapter 2), we provide a literature review about taxonomies and present the approach for constructing dimensions in this report. Subsequently (chapter 3), the methodological approach, material, and data that inform the taxonomy are presented. In chapter 4, we present the different dimensions of the channels of dissemination and their significance for scholarly strategies. In the concluding section (chapter 5), we provide an outlook of how the results of the various empirical activities will inform the taxonomy and stimulate wider debates.

2. Theoretical framework for constructing taxonomy of dissemination channels

Taxonomies are attempts to classify entities according to their properties and to certain dimensions (Bailey 1994). They have excluding and including effects on the entities of the social or physical world they claim to represent (Bowker, Star 1999). In academic settings, taxonomies are used to conceptualise complex phenomena with interrelated issues that are often not immediately conveyable (Smith 2002). By arranging and ordering different entities into specific categories, they reduce complexity and can provide a framework for debate (Greenberg 1987; Archibugi 2006), but also for intervention (Bradley et al. 2007). In this support activity, our task is to develop a taxonomy that provides orientation to scholars preparing or evaluating a dissemination strategy for their research output. Since dissemination of research is a complex phenomenon, many different aspects come to the fore of which not all can be related to the content but to cultural characteristics, such as routines, norms, and values of their target audiences.

As other types of frameworks such as theories, themes, or typologies, taxonomies are constructed through a complex interplay between reflection and observation. Yet different to typologies which are perceived to represent abstract concepts, taxonomies are understood to relate to ‘empirically observable and measurable characteristics (Smith 2002, p. 381). Hence, taxonomies are based on empirical observation and validation that relates to these characteristics. This often entails engaging experts or conducting surveys to explore perceptions or patterns of interpretation.

The empirical analysis and exploration that allows the specification of taxonomies, however, hinges on theoretical considerations that constitute and inform how a phenomenon is articulated and how

¹ http://openup-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/OpenUp-Deliverable_D5.1_Altmetrics-status-quo.pdf

dimensions are constructed that relate to each other.² In this project, we intend to construct a taxonomy of dissemination channels based on considerations from the sociology of valuation that provides key assumptions about how different scholarly services become relevant and valuable for scholarly dissemination and for what reasons. As outlined in a previous report, the basis for such theory making is that evaluation becomes more important (Power 1997) because of the increasing uncertainty and complexity in many different fields of society. This particularly accounts for scholarly communication and dissemination, which has been traditionally safeguarded by the institutions of peer review and other mechanisms of self-governance. These mechanisms of self-governance have provided scholarly dissemination channels such as articles, books and with value and appreciation both within and beyond the scholarly realm (Merton 1957, 1968). Moreover, a specific set of evaluation indicators and metrics has been constructed on these channels of dissemination and the way they refer to each other (e.g. in publications and citations). From the perspective of the sociology of valuation (Lamont 2012), these metrics have provided additional value to these channels since they represent abstract concepts such as performance or disciplinary recognition. With the advent of new channels of dissemination and the appreciation they are about to gain in different realms of society and their audiences, it becomes unclear how these are to be perceived and valorised. This task of OpenUp (5.2. and 5.4) seeks to contribute to a clarification in this respect. What we can interestingly observe is thus: value creation in the making.

In the previous report, we have argued that the way these channels are attributed value is through both their use and consumption. Specific qualities of these channels are infused with values which are regarded relevant for specific purposes. The qualities that these channels have for their users and their audiences, we have argued, cause their significance for scholarly communication since they are not necessarily explicitly known but put into action every single time a specific item is produced or consumed. Based on extensive literature review, we have called these action ‘acts as valuation’ whereby we classified various activities in digital scholarly services and social media to the following concepts: doing science and science made public (e.g. blogs, microblogs), referencing (Mendeley), entertainment (e.g. youtube, vimeo), stabilizing knowledge (Wikipedia, github etc.), recommending (e.g. f1000), and organizing attribution. In our framework, these acts of valuation constitute the phenomena to which different dimensions can be attached which will be outlined in the following sections.

The dimensions of these channels are constructed through various processes we explore. On the one hand, they are constructed through discourses that attribute value to a certain channel of communication by positioning them to a dominant narrative. In the realm of scholarly communication, such a dominant discourse is the discourse about research performance or research impact that can influence how a channel of dissemination can be valorised. For instance, the quantitatively informed research performance discourse has altered how book chapters are perceived. In a similar way, we argue, new discourses have developed that shape how a certain novel channel is perceived.

The second process, which influences how certain channels of dissemination are perceived, are cultural practices and routines. Becher and Trowler have put forward the idea that the different disciplines in science can be understood as specific tribes that govern a particular territory of science, challenging the notion that science is understood as an abstract unity (Becher, Trowler 1989). Specific practices and stances which have been incorporated through scientific socialization processes shape how a specific format of communicating science is performed. For instance, Charles Bazerman has shown how the structure and writing format of scientific research article shape how physical science is to be understood (Bazerman 1988). On the contrary in sociology, the production of large monographs value has long been highly recognized, as disciplinary histories reconstructed the field by referring to sociological founding fathers that made use of these formats (Weingart, Lepenies 1983). Through these culturally and field-specific writing and consumption habits, channels are attributed with value. New channels of dissemination, we propose, will to some extent be estimated against how appropriate they are in accordance with existing field specific valuations of certain channels of dissemination. In this respect, we might also expect generational differences that cut across these various domains of science.

² For example, in the case of policy studies, the most important taxonomy is constructed from the basic assumption that politics is caused by policies, hence, that political structures are the effects of the processual dimensions.

Thirdly and finally, we argue that the value of these channels of dissemination will be influenced by how they are integrated into metrics. Quantitative indicators in science strongly refer to categories of evaluation. Metrics are rarely neutral objects. Consequently, the significance of some communication channels might hinge on how they are tracked and counted. In addition, these counting and tracking activities of novel channels of dissemination are performed by specific providers who integrate several of these channels as data sources in their metric (e.g. PloS ALM, altmetric.com, Plum Analytics). These providers display differences as to how they relate and integrate these data sources. For scholarly strategies, that means that scholars might not only look at what channels they use, e.g. which kind of value they want to create by choosing a specific format, but also whether this kind of activity is covered by altmetrics providers that are most appropriate for their community.

Based on the above theoretical framework, our approach to covers the different channels of dissemination, their dimensions, and their valuation.

3. Approach, data, and methodology

3.1. General approach:

Based on these theoretical considerations, our aim is to study discourses, field specific perceptions, and metrics of innovative channels of dissemination. This empirical data will be used to inform and to specify the different dimensions related to the specific acts of valuation we proposed.

To study discourses around innovative dissemination and altmetrics, an analysis of scholarly publications and positions appears to be most suitable since these discourses are most likely to shape legitimate positions and thereby construct value to their use and consumption.

To study how innovative channels of dissemination are recognized, and to learn more about the structural aspects thereof, the most common technique is to develop and conduct a survey that can provide information about common perceptions. While this information can most likely reveal what is known and perceived relevant, more qualitative interviews reveal how the significance of certain dissemination channels is interpreted and what drives this interpretation that leads to value creation in scholarly and non-scholarly debates.

Finally, in order to create what Nowotny et al. call robust knowledge (Nowotny et al. 2001), the resulting knowledge taxonomy needs to be related to the relevant audiences and stakeholders in order to stimulate debate and allow for participation in creating reflexive resources (see also Deliverable 4.1. in this respect). All these different perspectives of inquiry demand different and tailored methods of data collection that need to be designed in accordance with the guiding research question of this activity, which is, constructing a theoretically informed and empirically grounded taxonomy of dissemination channels.

Within OpenUp, we can draw on various activities of data collection and exploration that meet these demands, which altogether allow for a triangulation and validation of the subject under study.

Firstly, to reconstruct dominant narratives and discourses, we build on a review of scholarly literature about Altmetrics and innovative dissemination channels, relating to Deliverables 4.1. and 5.1., respectively.

Secondly, to map perceptions and public understanding of these channels and altmetric indicators, we draw on a survey conducted within OpenUp that has been designed by all project participants coordinated and implemented by the coordinator. These data allow specifying general structures and field-specific information. These data will also allow for integrating gender related aspects.

Thirdly, these data is validated by explorative interviews with experts in the field in order to reconstruct dominant interpretive patterns.

Finally, all this information is synthesized and discussed with interested communities to further deepen the resulting taxonomy. In the following, we provide data and method of each activity in detail.

3.2. Data, methods, and preliminary results

3.2.1. Analysis of scholarly discourse

Firstly, we can build on previous work in Deliverable 5.1. In that report, we have analysed a corpus of around 320 articles and position papers to reconstruct the landscape of how innovative dissemination channels are framed (see Appendix A for details). By applying bibliometric and informetric methods in attempts of constructing the corpus (see Moed et al. 2004 for an overview), we revealed which communities were active and thus particularly shaped their meaning, which is, informetric and scientometric community. We observed a sharp increase of publications on these topics allowing for predicting with some uncertainty that the debate towards dissemination is continuing to thrive. After having grouped and classified these various pieces of communication, we have identified two major discourses to which innovative dissemination is related. Probably, it is these channels that do not only frame how innovative dissemination and altmetrics are understood but that also influence their recent uptake.

The first discourse to which Altmetrics is related to is the discourse on research performance and impact of research (Bornmann, Leydesdorff 2013; Costas et al. 2014; James Wilsdon et al. 2015). Again, this discourse is deeply related to narratives of informetrics and scientometrics. We have found that there is a strong tendency, to relate scholarly uses of social media to research to existing indicators of scientific output, e.g. publications and citations. This is not only reflected in theoretical considerations about how to interpret social media use and altmetrics but also in dominant practices of counting. What we could observe is a strong increase of scrutinization activities, where the coverage and distribution of various social media data sources are empirically investigated, mostly measured against existing indicators of influence such as citations. The greater a certain channel displays (positive) correlation with citations and publications, the more likely it is that this channel is interpreted to indicate research performance. As a result, we do not only have a vast amount of correlation studies of Altmetrics data sources, but also a specific discursive context in which scholarly media use is presented and related to, that is, research impact and research impact measurement. This discourse shapes not only how Altmetrics is perceived, but also attributes value to the various channels of dissemination upon which the alternative indicators rest. We will come back later to that point.

A second discourse we have identified throughout the analysis of scholarly literature is the discourse on societal impact (Bornmann 2014, 2016; Cress 2014). The discourse on societal impact can be perceived as an alternative narrative or as counter-narrative of the research performance discourse. Contrary to the research performance, this discourse is particularly fuelled by policy discourse that tends to reflect growing expectations towards the uses and applications of science and technology. Similarly to the structure and pattern of the research performance discourse, we did not only find articles that generally articulate the societal value of novel channels of dissemination on a theoretical level, but also articles that used societal impact as an interpretive scheme. That is, whenever, a certain type of dissemination channel is not correlated to citations or publication coverage, these articles then tend to interpret this channel as indicating some 'other type of impact' or more often even 'societal impact'. While it is not often clear what societal impact means in these specific contexts, the data show that scholars need to relate to this discourse in some respect. Currently, we could not completely reconstruct, how this discourse emerged since it appears to go beyond the scholarly realm, nevertheless the dominance of its occurrence reveals its significance for scholarly dissemination strategies.

Thus, we have identified two discourses from scholarly literature that specify dimensions of how innovative dissemination is interpreted and positioned. We can assume that these discourses also influence perceptions of scholars.

3.2.2. Secondary analysis of survey results

The second source of information that feeds into the construction of dimensions related to dissemination channels results from a general survey that has been set up within OpenUP (see Appendix B). Almost 1000 scholars responded to the survey, coming from various disciplines, such as the natural sciences, engineering, but also medicine and the social sciences. Beside other items, the survey also

asked for (traditional and innovative) channels of dissemination and altmetrics use as well as their disciplinary recognition (Question batteries Q3 and Q4). These findings allow for articulating which types of media are appreciated and how they are perceived in different disciplinary communities. We have grouped the different answers towards what channels of dissemination they appreciate to their disciplinary background and their sociodemographic characteristics. A detailed list of these activities will be provided in an upcoming report.

The data reveal that there are strong field-specific differences towards the recognition, use, and appreciation of innovative dissemination channels. While the natural sciences and the engineering sciences often make less use of them, the social sciences and the humanities seem to be more informed and more likely to use these new formats (Q 3.5) though the use of these channels is still very low (with the exemption of academic social network sites). The data also reveal that appreciation of certain channels hinges to a large extent on which practices are appropriate in the respective field. For instance, we can observe that traditional channels of dissemination are particularly favoured in the natural sciences where they are also most frequently used. In addition, there are also strong intergenerational differences, depending on the age of the scholars: The younger generations both in the social sciences and in the natural sciences, have a stronger tendency to use novel channels while they are also more aware of these channels (relating to 3.8). Thus, both of these dimensions, field specificity and intergenerational assessment, structure how the channels are used and perceived. In an upcoming activity, we plan to map and to cluster these various qualities in order to further provide more specific information useful for characterizing a target audience for dissemination channels (see also Bailey 1994). For instance, it might be relevant to specifically focus on social sciences juniors or on natural sciences seniors in order to develop a dedicated dissemination strategy.

Finally, the survey results also revealed how dominant narratives and discourses literally influenced the perceptions of scholars, particularly in the perception of Altmetrics. This applies for the discourse on societal impact which is particularly dominant in the overall reading of innovative dissemination channels and altmetrics. Although only a few know what is meant by the term Altmetrics – only a third of the respondents know what it means exactly - a vast number of scholars interprets scholarly social media use to point at societal impact (responses related to Q 4.4. and 4.5.). This indicates a strong effect of the dominant discourse on the subject. It thereby validates our findings from the analysis of the scholarly literature and encourages us to this as a dimension for our dissemination channel taxonomy.

3.2.3. Qualitative interviews with experts in the field

As we do not know exactly how these interpretive patterns emerged and how the appreciation of value in these settings can be understood, we draw on qualitative interviews with experts in scholarly social media use and altmetrics. These experts have been identified in a review about scholarly output which has been performed in Task 5.1. In addition, experts in the field of policy and research funding agencies have been integrated into the list to broaden the scope of interviewees (see Appendix C – the List of Interviewees). Until now, we have already developed a guideline for conducting semi-structured qualitative inquiry that is constantly improved (see Appendix for details). Though results of some of the interviews are preliminary, we can already present some of them which allow for deepening the dimensions identified in the review and the survey activity.

In an upcoming activity, the results of the interviews will be documented and transcribed. We will then iteratively summarize, analyze, and code the material applying methods of qualitative content analysis (Glaser, Strauss Anselm L. 2010; Kuckartz 2014). Beside the existing theoretical concepts, we have developed so far, we hope to derive some more subcodes in the material that specify the dimensions of appreciation and valuation of dissemination channels in this context. These information will also allow for constructing relations between the different dimensions developed so far (Bradley et al. 2007, p. 1766)

3.2.4. Analysis of metrics related to innovative channels of dissemination

Fourthly, we will also map metrics and metric activities that track and count different aspects of each dissemination channel and each service. In part, we can draw on previous knowledge gained within OpenUP (Deliverable 4.1. and 5.1.). This is done because, as we have argued in chapter 2, that

classifications from evaluative activities further contribute to value creation as they allow for comparison and putting certain qualities into an order or a range. By so doing, certain measurable aspects become more visible. In the field of innovative dissemination channels and altmetrics, these measuring activities are moderated and mediated by certain data providers who define what data sources from which channel are tracked and how this translates into a specific indicator. Thereby, certain aspects of social media use, specific assumptions about what constitutes value for scholarly communication are inscribed into every indicator. By linking these indicators to publisher sites and personal webpages, indicators such as the altmetric.com composite indicator, create visibility for a set or for a specific channel of dissemination. In an upcoming activity, we plan to relate these data from metrics of the providers to information about scholarly perceptions of dissemination channels gained from the survey. We will thus be able, for instance, to provide information of whether a certain provider meets the expectations and appreciations of a specific field.

3.2.5. Documentation and analysis of stakeholder workshop

Finally, we have encouraged the communities to engage with the taxonomy dimensions in a workshop held in Berlin. Scholars from various disciplines, policy makers, research managers and altmetrics experts have been invited to discuss the findings. The workshop has been held on the premises of the WPL and gained considerable awareness in the community.

In the following, we will provide the results of the activities that are relevant for our taxonomy, including the survey conducted within OpenUp, the results of expert interviews, and the documentation of workshops. Results of the review of scholarly literature will not be reported here (see Deliverable D 5.1) for details. The results of all activities will be integrated in the tables in section 4.4.

4. Results

4.1. Secondary analysis of Survey results within OpenUp

4.1.1. Goals of analysis

In order to provide an analysis for the appreciation of different communication channels, we can rely on a survey conducted within OpenUP (see Appendix B for details). This information will be used to specify the taxonomy generated in 4.3.

More specifically, the aim of this analysis is to address two questions regarding the relationship between different innovative and traditional channels of dissemination and the assessment of researchers regarding the utility of these channels. First, what are patterns of different uses of these channels of dissemination taking into account scientific disciplines? Second, are there generational differences within these fields regarding the assessment of channels of dissemination?

4.1.2. Data Source

The analysis is based on the OpenUp survey conducted at the end of 2016 among researchers identified through their correspondence address. In total, 976 cases were collected. In order to allow for a granular analysis that takes into account both the level of career stage as well as a notion of disciplinary differences we had to merge respondents into broader fields due to the relatively low absolute number of early level researchers. Two fields were constructed to allow for comparison. One field comprises “Social Science & Humanities” (N=210), the other field consists of “Natural Science & Engineering” (N=608) and is based on a merge of respondents from natural science, engineering and computer science. The fields were chosen to represent rather differently focused fields that both in their methods as well as in their questions and research goals are rather different. For each of the disciplinary groups four different types of relevances and uses were analyzed. These represent the use of channels of disseminations as means of promoting and diffusing your work (Disseminate), as means of informing your work as a researcher (Inform), as a recognized and valuable activity within the respondents field

(Appreciate) and as having potential to lead to societal impact (Society). The four dimensions were covered by four survey questions:

- "Which of these channels listed do you use most frequently to disseminate your own research to reach your target groups?" (Disseminate)
- "How frequently do you use these sources to inform your professional work as a researcher?" (Inform)
- "Please rate how being represented in these dissemination activities is generally appreciated within your field of research" (Appreciate)
- "What potential do the following dissemination channels have to lead to a wider societal impact?" (Society)

For each question a battery of different dissemination channels was assessed on a Likert scale. In total 19 channels of dissemination were assessed in the survey including one "other" category which did not enter analysis. The assessed channels through the survey and in this analysis are:

- Traditional academic publishing (e.g. academic journals, books)
- Popular science publications (e.g. magazines)
- Academic conferences/workshops
- Events for the general public/specific target audiences other than researchers
- Press releases
- Television/radio programs
- Open access repositories/ preprint servers (e.g. Zenodo, arXiv)
- Academic social networks (e.g. ResearchGate, Academia.edu)
- Non-specialist social networks (e.g. Facebook, Twitter)
- Podcasts, Video sharing sites (e.g. YouTube, Vimeo)
- Wikipedia
- Blogs, other wikis (excluding Wikipedia)
- E-Mail/Newsletters
- Personal/Project Website
- Open lab books/interactive notebooks
- Print media (e.g. leaflets, folders)
- Git repositories (e.g. GitHub)
- Exhibitions, performances

4.1.3. Methodology

For each permutation of the groups to be analyzed, i.e. 2x2 table for natural science vs. social science and junior level researchers vs. senior level researcher, the share of respondents were calculated that assessed a channel as high or very high for each of the question relative to the total number of valid responses for these questions. The resulting data tables were then visualized using two-dimensional heat maps. The individual channels of dissemination were visualized as rows of the heat map. The columns of the heat map consist of the four uses (Disseminate, Inform, Appreciate, and Society). Each dimension was clustered based on the initial raw data for the group to be analyzed. The cluster analysis was based on a cosine-transformed distance matrix and employed the Ward algorithm as agglomeration method. The distance calculation was checked for robustness by using different distance functions. The heat maps were constructed to capture the range of 0 to 1, i.e. 0% to 100% of respondents. The shades of the heat map cells represent the percentage share of respondents assessing this combination of channel and use dimension as high or very high: the darker the shade, the higher the share. To allow for a better visual assessment, each cell includes a vertical line, which also comprises the value represented in the cell. Each heat map includes a color key to account for the overall distribution of the assessment.

4.1.4. Results

In a first step we assessed the inter-generational differences within each discipline, specifically taking into account In the second step we analyzed the intra-generational differences across disciplines.³

Natural Sciences & Engineering

The results of our analysis for the discipline of natural science shows that there is a stable pattern of assessment for the dimensions of Dissemination, Appreciation and Information for traditional codified modes of knowledge diffusion through publications in peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings (see Figure 1; Figure 2). Regarding innovative channels of dissemination we find that natural science juniors assess a higher societal impact of Podcasts and web-based Videos ($p < .001$), and activities on generic social networks ($p < .001$), compared to natural science seniors. Similar is true but to a lesser extent for Wikis ($p < .05$), Blogs ($p < .1$) and Code Repositories ($p < .1$).

Figure 1: Heat map of assessment of dissemination channels for junior researchers from natural science & engineering

Source: OpenUp Survey; Calculations: DZHW

Figure 2: Heat map of assessment of dissemination channels for senior researchers from natural science & engineering

³ Comparisons are based on Mann-Whitney tests performed on the ordinal variables. P values are adjusted to control the false discovery rate (Benjamini & Yekutieli, 2001).

Source: OpenUp Survey; Calculations: DZHW

Social Science & Humanities

In the case of Social Science & Humanities (see Figure 3; Figure 4) we find a similar pattern regarding established modes of codified knowledge dissemination with high values in the Inform, Disseminate & Appreciate Dimensions and average values for Societal Impact. We also find that, especially for social science junior researchers the pattern of differentiation between different channels regarding their societal impact is less clear cut compared to the situation in the natural sciences. In contrast, we find a much cleared cut notion of appreciation within the field for social science senior researchers compared to all other cases we analyzed. For social science seniors appreciation for innovative forms of dissemination is assessed as rather low. Like in the case of natural science & engineering we find a pronounced difference in the assessment of societal impact for Podcasts & web-based videos ($p < .001$) and generic social network activities ($p < .001$) with significantly more junior researchers assessing a high level of societal impact for these channels. We also find that in the case of Social Science & Humanities the share of junior researchers attributing high potential for societal impact is uniformly higher in all dimensions compared to their senior counterparts. Yet, these differences are not statistically significant and might be a statistical artefact.

Figure 3: Heat map of assessment of dissemination channels for junior researchers from social science & humanities

Source: OpenUp Survey; Calculations: DZHW

Figure 4: Heat map of assessment of dissemination channels for senior researchers from social science & humanities

Source: OpenUp Survey; Calculations: DZHW

Cross-disciplinary assessment

Comparing both junior level and senior level researchers between fields shows that regarding the dimension of societal impact natural science seniors generally seem to attribute a higher societal impact on all dissemination channels compared to senior level researchers in the social sciences. The highest differences can be found for OpenAccess Repositories ($p < .05$), Wikis ($p < .1$) and Art ($p < .1$). Regarding the comparison on junior level we find the opposite effect with natural science juniors seeming more sceptical compared to their social science counterparts. The strongest differences we find for activities in generic social networks ($p < .05$) as well as academic social networks ($p < .05$) and to a lesser extend for Popular Science ($p < .1$). This result suggests that in Natural Science & Engineering there is a stronger harmonized inter-generationally shared notion of valuation regimes both regarding the three dimensions of Disseminate, Inform & Appreciate as well as regarding Societal Impact. In the social sciences & humanities these valuation regimes seem to differ more in terms of the breadth of assessment of the impact of channels of dissemination on societal impact. Overall, junior level researchers seem to be more open to the idea of societal impact of innovative dissemination channels. Yet, these differences are not uniformly statistically significant.

In total we find a cross-cutting pattern of clusters of channels of dissemination based on their correlation within the four dimensions Disseminate, Inform, Appreciate & Societal Impact (see Figure 5). The cluster analysis is based on the same method as the calculation visualized by the heat maps.

Figure 5: Hierarchical Clusters of Channels of Dissemination

Source: OpenUp Survey; Calculations: DZHW

In total, we can isolate five clusters of dissemination channels:

- **Traditional codified channels** (Academic Publishing, Conferences)
- **Traditional Public Understanding of Science (PUSH) channels** (Press, Radio, TV, Popular Science Books, Public Events)
- **Innovative Science 2.0 PUSH channels** (Art, Wikis, Generic Social Networks, Podcasts & Videos)
- **Progress Channels** (Blogs, Project Websites, Newsletters, Print Media)
- **Sharing Channels** (Open Lab Books, OA Repositories, Academic Social Networks, Code Repositories)

4.1.5. Conclusions

Even though, these clusters of dissemination channels seem to be largely robust across the analyzed groups the actual extent of each channel on the four dimensions rather than the structural similarities differ across groups. Yet, they can provide useful information when interpreting the taxonomy as they also can represent substitution channels that share similar properties on the Disseminate, Inform, Appreciate, Society dimensions. Yet, such an assessment has to be made with caution relative to the target group which ought to be addressed. Using the data at hand, we can only assess the notions of researcher's vis-à-vis their assessment of societal impact. In total, even though the overall structure of channels of dissemination seem to follow a plausible order, differences between fields and status groups of researchers have to be taken into account when using the taxonomy developed in this report. These differences between fields for the appreciation of altmetrics have been also accounted for in the expert interviews as the next section shows.

4.2. Results from expert interviews

The data from the survey has generated general assessments for the perception and appreciation of novel communication channels. However, in order to reconstruct more specifically how the relationships between these novel channels of dissemination and Altmetrics can be understood, we have conducted interviews with experts from different fields. The results of this undertaking will also be used to further specify the significance and the problems for specific channels of communication.

More specifically, the aim for conducting expert interviews was to gather different views and perceptions on altmetrics. Besides providing critical views towards altmetrics, we also aimed at reconstructing how the community or field of altmetrics is linked to various scholarly and non-scholarly debates.

Table 1: Stakeholder diversity

Stakeholder group	Number of interviewees
Scholarly experts (scientometricians, informetricians, computer scientists)	6
Publishers	5
Digital scholarly services provider (including platform provider, altmetric data provider, meta data provider)	7
Open Science activists	2
Policy advisors	2
Total	22

Source: Own compilation (DZHW)

We were able to interview experts and stakeholders from heterogeneous settings and backgrounds such as publishers, data base providers (including representative from all altmetric data providers), librarians, established service providers, and scholars from the field of scientometrics and bibliometrics. Altogether we conducted more than 20 expert interviews with a minimum duration of one hour in the period between March and July 2017. The interviews have been recorded and analysed according to the categories of our interview guideline. Adapting the guideline to the specific competences of the interviews, we asked questions that can be specified in the following way.

Since we were interested in how new channels dissemination are linked with Altmetrics, we asked not only about the perception of Altmetrics but first of all focused on how novel tools of dissemination are perceived and used in the specific fields. In a subsequent set of questions, we then focussed on the role of Altmetrics in the proliferation of these channels. Other questions were aiming at reconstructing perceptions of Altmetrics as a field in general and in relation to existing debates: How is Altmetrics perceived in the scholarly world as well as in the field of practitioners and providers of scientific infrastructures and metadata? Furthermore, we asked for the drivers in the current debate and the role different actors and stakeholders play in this movement. In these cases, interviewees were also expressing perceptions as to how Altmetrics is changing the existing ecosystems of scholarly research communication, publishing, and dissemination. Finally, we asked as to how current debates about impact assessment and evaluation are related to Altmetrics. In particular, we were interested in how interviewees perceive the relationship between Altmetrics and the debate about measuring societal impact.

Since we have interviewed actors from many different fields and stakeholder groups, answers were diverse and perceptions about Altmetrics and its drivers greatly differed. Most of these differences can be related to the interests and roles of their organization or their position in the research and publishing world, leading to emphasis on different issues and providing accounts of different granularity. Furthermore, we were also able to identify and map expectations towards what each actor in the research and publishing interface should accomplish (e.g. funders, publishers, data and meta data providers, service providers, scholarly organizations). As a result, we now have a landscape of expert opinions that allow for specifying different parts of the taxonomy (e.g. who is contributing to valuation of innovative channels of dissemination, who is contributing to valuing metrics, who is or is expected to provide infrastructure). In other words, we are in the position to elaborate on and to distinguish between on the one hand accounts that relate to structural dimensions and dynamics at the communication channels side, on the other hand we could also identify accounts that lead us to dynamics of the metrics and the metrics providers, and finally we can find identify accounts that point at interrelations between the two. Thereby, the current taxonomy does not only provide a perspective of how these two sides are related to each other, but it also reflects the structures and dynamics of the current ecosystem of research and publishing including metadata providers, service providers, digital platforms, publishers and researchers.

4.2.1. Perception of novel communication and dissemination channels

As we can see from the interviews, novel channels of dissemination and Altmetrics are regarded an important topic in the world of scholarly communication. We can see that a new media ecology with new infrastructures and channels has developed that is greatly supported by new tools of digitalization. There are now more possibilities to express opinions and more forms of output that can be disseminated to scholarly and sometimes also non-scholarly audiences. Yet the interviewees not only outlined that these channels need to be analysed and treated with caution, they also greatly differed as to which of these channels were considered relevant. Interviewees coming from an Open Science background greatly emphasized the value of novel tools for sharing and collaboration (interviewee 13, 16) while interviewees of some of the service providers also emphasized the need of using channels for organizing and accumulating attention (interviewee 8, 10). The overall consensus was that the value of each channel of communication should be judged separately.

Similar to the results from the survey, most of the interviewees agreed that the established and traditional forms of communication stay most important and are valuable for scholars since they will continue to structure careers and organizational paths. This is further revealed by the fact that most interviewees admitted that social media tools are only partly relevant for their daily work life either as researchers or as research managers. Repeatedly interviewees used the quote: ‘You will not get a job for your [prominent social media platform] posts’ to show that the relevance of new dissemination needs to be judged in relation to existing incentives. ‘As long as we do not have a change in the reward system of science, nothing of these practices will become institutionally relevant’ as argued by an interviewee from the field of bibliometrics.

New forms of output, however, are expected to become more important to promote research and to stay in contact with the research community. The increasing competitive pressure on researchers is perceived to increase demand for developing strategies aiming at generating attention which will increasingly lead to tailored communications for different audiences.

‘Scholars will speak different languages using different concepts and different channels when talking to different people’ (interviewee 10).

In this respect, the new landscape of social media and web-based forms of scholarly communication are becoming more important. Some of the interviewees emphasized that new forms of intervention already help in building up and gathering new scholarly resources for evolving, often interdisciplinary communities. As an effect, there is increasing pressure on scholars not only to publish and present themselves, but also to administrate and orchestrate their (self-)presentations. In this respect, new sources and tools such as ORCID will become more relevant that serve researchers and allow for ‘populating’ (interviewee 8) various platforms with specified information. Particularly from the perspective of publishers, metadata and service providers these, organizations and resources are highly valued.

4.2.2. Perception of Altmetrics

This overall consensus among interviewees in how new channels of dissemination are perceived disappeared when it comes to perceptions about Altmetrics and its uses for research and research management. Interviewee’s present very different views as to how Altmetrics should be interpreted and on what occasions it becomes relevant. Starting with the term of Altmetrics, many interviewees expressed their dissatisfaction. Relating to the above mentioned channels of dissemination, some interviewees argued that Altmetrics should be simply defined as social media based metrics of scholarly output. Others strongly disagreed with the claim of being alternative, criticizing the ‘alt’ part of Altmetrics. They see these metrics as part of a larger set of metrics that just point at different things. Particularly from the perspective of scholarly data provider such claims of being alternative were highly criticized. Now, it is argued, Altmetrics have been integrated in a landscape of scholarly services and products and have thereby rather become a ‘complementary’ (interviewee 17) rather than alternative set of metrics.

There also differences on how Altmetrics are perceived on a more abstract level: While we find the view particularly from open science activists that Altmetrics can be interpreted as a set of tools and techniques for evaluation, interviewees from the scholarly field classified Altmetrics mostly as ‘a subfield of scientometrics and bibliometrics’. According to these interviewees, there is now a lively debate as to how the new uses of scholarly tools can be related to established sets of indicators in scientometrics. At the same time, the uncertainty over what these metrics signify stand in sharp opposition to established indicators of scientometrics and bibliometrics such as citations. Different to Altmetrics data- such as views or downloads- ‘citations are deeply rooted in the system as accepted scholarly conventions’ and much expertise has been accumulated as to how citations can be interpreted. That is why, according to this view, Altmetrics is viewed as ‘additional’ source of information in scientometric and bibliometric analyses.

Other interviewees particularly from the field of data providers and digital scholarly services, however, saw Altmetrics to be more than a scientific subfield, but a vibrant community of activists engaging in providing and tailoring different data services to support not only researchers but also publishers, editors of scientific journals, funders and policy makers while the scholarly debate covers only small aspects of these interrelations. This community benefits from the diversity and the creativity which new data services provide. According to their perception, though Altmetrics are still to be further developed and integrated, they have reached a high level of awareness among different stakeholders. Such visibility, it is argued cannot be ignored.

Thus, we could observe differences in what aspects of the debate in Altmetrics have been emphasized among the stakeholders. While in the scholarly field, much emphasis has been put on the analysis and construction of indicators in Altmetrics, scholarly service providers and publishers emphasized the demand for analysing effects of the integration of Altmetrics data in the research and publishing

ecosystem.⁴ A third emphasis has been made by activists of open science: they argue that Altmetrics can be viewed as a means to create awareness and recognition for new practices of sharing and collaborating. Some of the respondents viewed Altmetrics as part of a cultural change in science towards an environment that is less dominated core journals and hence a dedicated journal culture. These interviewees saw a major challenge in building a new scientific infrastructure that will be accompanied with new forms of organizing attention and visibility to topics, fields, and communities which is now being done by some of the big publishers. There have been, however, some general remarks for the importance of the phenomenon; there have been diverging opinions as to whether Altmetrics will be influential for the change of the system of scholarly communication.

Such differences can be attributed to the different roles of stakeholders in the debate of Altmetrics: While publishers and service providers saw the demand of providing new and rich data and novel services for the production and dissemination of research, scholars from scientometrics and informetrics were confronted with expectations of providing complex information for research evaluation.

4.2.3. Drivers in Altmetrics

Different views can be also established regarding the question as to what the drivers of Altmetrics are. There are basically two common narratives prevalent in the corpus of interviews. According to the first narrative, drivers of Altmetrics can be rooted in feelings of dissatisfaction with existing metrics and indicators for scholarly evaluation, such as the ubiquitous use of citation statistics (interviewee 1, 11, 3, 6, 7, 8). This narrative is highly consistent with the justifications of Altmetrics propagators such as Jason Priem who coined the term in 2010. Jason Priem argued that citations have long dominated the scientific value system. Resistance against the journal impact factor is also considered to be one of the reasons why the debate about Altmetrics has been taken up so strongly by scholarly activists. According to the service and meta data providers, there appears to be a scholarly demand to provide metrics on the level of individual research output rather than on the journal level. Some open science activists even argue that such journal based metrics should be overcome in general since in the future, journals should be less important than they are now. According to the interviewees, this route has been strongly taken up by the publishers who would now provide more services to promote research of their authors. A smaller but relevant proportion of interviewees emphasized the role of publishers in the proliferation of Altmetrics. The diffusion of Altmetrics in the scholarly world has been greatly pushed by their attempts to fund Altmetrics research and in integrating new data in established meta data services. Publishers are thus a key driver of Altmetrics since they drive the demand for services in the scholarly world.

On the other hand, there is a second narrative that situates the drivers of Altmetrics at the funder's side. Policy actors and funding agencies increasingly insist on producing new forms of output which they often frame as the societal impact of research. It has been argued that the Research Excellence Framework (REF) in the UK can be interpreted as one expression of these changes in the funding landscape. Researchers and scholars according to this view adapt to these changing funding conditions due to an increasingly competitive environment. Altmetrics in this respect can be related to these demands as a new metrics and evaluation schemes from the funders and policy side. These interpretations of Altmetrics as a potential indication for societal impact have according to some of the interviewees something to do with the penetration and dissemination of social media in society. As we can see from the list of data sources in Altmetrics, social media form a relevant part of communication channels related to Altmetrics. There are however doubts as to whether Altmetrics could really measure societal impact. Most interviewees are cautious with such claims of capability as most of the indicators

⁴ On their website, altmetric.com provide case studies of publishing houses who aimed to engage and use Altmetrics. We find following case about the publishing house Taylor & Francis: „Taylor & Francis took a number of steps to announce and introduce the launch of Altmetric data across their journals to their key stakeholders. This included blog posts for specific audiences (such as editors, authors and their wider readership), promotion in newsletters, an ongoing social media campaign across all channels, and the building of a Top 20 microsite to highlight the research that had generated the most online engagement across their portfolio.“

<https://www.altmetric.com/case-studies/taylor-francis-group/>

measure and are supposed to measure ‘attention’ rather than impact. Some of the service providers argue that the measurement of attention has not been central for the construction of these metrics. Other interviewees see a general potential to use Altmetrics to point at societal impact. New opportunities to capture Wikipedia for instance would allow for relating more directly to knowledge transfer in society. In the current form, however, much of the metrics are not consistent or not reliable enough to be used as a basis for such measures. Even twitter data – which are widely used in Altmetrics – can only partly be harvested leading to the question which data of twitter are represented. Furthermore, social media use in general- besides their increase in use - is still not representative for society at large. Scholars from the scientometric and bibliometric field argue that social media might be only one additional source for conceptualizing societal impact, but there are other sources for impact which might be still relevant such as collaborations with industry, engagement with civil society, public debates and many more. Besides these doubts and criticisms, however, all interviewees observed the increasing relevance of this debate as one of the drivers for the uptake of Altmetrics in the scholarly community.

4.2.4. Data sources in Altmetrics

One of the most critical parts of Altmetrics is the discussion about data sources in Altmetrics. There are many different views towards data in Altmetrics that have been expressed from experts and stakeholders for this report. These expert opinions not only allow for landscaping views but have also provided perspectives for how to structure the debate on data sources in Altmetrics. According to a scholarly expert in the field of scientometrics, data sources in Altmetrics can be distinguished between new forms of references for traditional output on the one hand (such as mentions of publications in tweets, in Facebook posts or in mendeley readings) and new forms of output such as blogs and recommendations.

Today, Altmetrics is related to a vast amount of different data sources that are captured and used to measure various different things. According to the interviewees, the social media data sources appear to be most relevant for the public perception of Altmetrics as Altmetrics is perceived by some of the experts as social media metrics. The provision of these data sources in Altmetrics studies is strongly structured by specific altmetric providers.⁵ As they have specific access to data services run by twitter or Facebook, they provide the community of researchers and publishers with pre-processed data for a variety of these sources. Hence, it increasingly becomes relevant to analyse the role of these new actors for the conduct of research related to these sources. In this regard, most of the interviewees perceive them as positive as most providers engage with the community and provide instant access to its data. In a similar vein, the data PloS provides to its authors are considered relevant and trustworthy. One of the interviewees therefore interprets the role of the providers as ‘data curators’ for the Altmetrics field. Since this role is perceived to be important for researchers, there have been pleas for less processed data from these providers. Yet some of the interviewees also see the risk of being too dependent on these source providers as they might decide to more strongly restrict access to some of the relevant data. Others expressed concerns about the commercial nature of this activity. They recommend a community owned service which would guarantee access to these data as some kind of scholarly infrastructure.

Increasingly, however, we have many new data sources which are also provided by these actors and there are different views as to whether this development can be interpreted and valued. To some interviewees, coming mainly from the field of open science, publishers and service providers, these new data sources are viewed as being positive for research evaluation and assessment as many new aspects could come to fore. It is argued that new opportunities would arise to capture the relevance and quality of research and to get rewards for research. Nevertheless, more effort should be spent on making these data more meaningful and relevant. As by now, we already have the opportunity to classify and sort publications by different criteria than citations alone. In this respect the upcoming data provide opportunities to classify and gather research output according to the needs of specific communities.

⁵ The landscape of altmetric data providers has been intensively discussed in Deliverable D 5.1 of this project.

On the other hand, however, the ever emerging amount of data sources is viewed as problematic. In particular, scholars expressed concerns about the increasing amount of data and the scraping and data collection practices that accompany them. In this view, the current dynamic expansion of Altmetrics data sources is driven by very technical and infrastructural capabilities, such as the accessibility to data through APIs and eventually to a lesser extent driven by conceptual scrutinizations. In other words: activities of integrating new data in Altmetrics indicators are to some extent accomplished because they can be measured. By so doing, the Altmetrics movement can be clearly associated to a regime of quantification that seems to reach every realm of life. On the other hand, the data providers argue, some of the sources which might be of relevance cannot be used because they do not provide interfaces or they do not provide data on a relevant level of granularity. Some of the sources that have been viewed as relevant through the community and ecosystem ties of the provider could thus not be captured. So in this way, technical capabilities like for instance, the accessibility of data through APIs can be interpreted as both enabling and constraining force for the intergration of data sources in Altmetrics.

4.2.5. Data sources and the construction and interpretation of indicators in Altmetrics

Classifications, categorizations, are more problematic when different data sources are aggregated, weighted and ranked in specific ways to construct metrics. In this regard, many of the interviewees insisted particularly on the transparent and open construction of these new rankings and metrics. In some cases, there are no indications of how the metrics and algorithms are constructed which is perceived as a problem particularly for scholars in the field. In addition, the implementation of some of these metrics can have performative effects or as some interviewees have put it – perverse – effects on the research community as they allow for manipulation. Some of the providers therefore argue that the weighting of sources already reflects the probability of manipulation. In any case as has been argued by various interviewees, composite indicators bear a lot of different problems since the separate interpretation of each data source often appears to be more meaningful.

Thus, according to many interviewees, new alternative metrics have to be interpreted with caution. Service providers and publishers therefore increasingly point at using these metrics in their specific contexts. For instance, the number of twitter counts alone will tell less about the reasons why this has been tweeted. Therefore, content analyses and contextualised information for metrics might be more relevant in the future. In general more efforts are needed in order to understand what these metrics and statistics could mean or signify. In this respect, stakeholders, scholars and publishers are encouraged to more closely work together.

Such metric sensitive collaboration is particularly in the realms of evaluation and impact assessment. To some interviewees from the scholarly field this seemed to be the only relevant usage of Altmetrics. Interviewees mainly agreed upon that some of the Altmetrics data sources could be used as early indicators for research performance assessments since they are highly correlated with citations. This, however, is to be done with caution and cannot be generalized for all forms and channels of dissemination.

4.3. A taxonomy of data sources linked to Altmetrics

In this section, the information generated in the different inquiries will be finally used to define a taxonomy of dissemination channels. This taxonomy will cover different aspects that are relevant for how these channels can be interpreted. The aspects – or dimensions – for assessing these channels have been explored through various activities of this project by reviewing literature, surveying scholars, and discussing input with stakeholders. Based on the sociology of evaluation, we have grouped the various scholarly services that are debated and used within altmetrics according to different acts of valuation such as doing science and science made public, explaining and entertaining, organizing attribution, empowering reproducibility, recommending, stabilizing knowledge, and supporting policy. In a previous report, we provided the argument for such a methodology.

In the following, we provide a list of tables that covers different groups of services and thus dissemination linking them with relevant information about how they are appreciated and valued both within and across a specific field. By so doing, we aim to provide orientation for scholars who plan to develop a dissemination strategy and are unsure about how what might be relevant in this respect and

how a certain choice of communication is appreciated within their community. Each table, e.g. each group of services – covers the following aspects:

- **Attention:** This category contains information about how channels of dissemination have the potential to increase attention for different types scientific output. The data for this category have been derived from the interviews conducted as well as desk research. It has to be noted that the assessment of attention can under the current situation not be fully disentangled according to target groups. Yet, in a further activity the findings that went into constructing the taxonomy will be harmonized with the findings from WP4 and WP6.
- **General scholarly appreciation:** This category informs about how a specific communication channel is appreciated across various scholarly audiences. The data for this category have been derived from the survey which was conducted within OpenUp. It contains information about whether scholars find a specific communication channel valuable for their scholarly communication. Note: these perceptions are based on individual assessments of researchers in a survey, not on expert opinions. Again, it must be mentioned that dissemination channels beyond established scholarly communication formats such as conference presentations and publications only rarely receive reward and are only to a lesser extent appreciated in general.
- **Scholarly relevance:** This category contains information as to whether a specific channel of communication has been attributed to be scholarly relevant. We use the term 'scholarly relevant' as a general term for denoting as to whether a specific channel or service is of importance for either supporting scholarly workflows or is considered to be useful for addressing specific audiences with scholarly information. The assessment is based on an analysis of the scholarly expert literature in scientometrics, bibliometrics and information science conducted in activity D 5.2. and does not provide a representative perception across all sciences. To give an example, blogs are considered as 'scholarly relevant' because a number of scholarly articles in this specific literature have treated them as relevant for communicating scholarly arguments to non-scientific audiences. Recommendations in f1000prime may be considered as scholarly relevant as they can provide important information about the quality of a research article. At the contrary, Twitter mentions may direct attention to a specific research output but they themselves rarely contain or provide any scholarly argument.
- **Field specific appreciation:** This category contains information as to whether the appreciation of a specific communication channel is field specific or not. Some channels of communication are particularly appreciated and used in specific disciplines or scientific fields. There are, for instance, differences in how twitter is assessed among the scholarly communities. The information is based on results from the survey, analysis of scholarly literature as well as expert opinions.
- **Provider coverage:** This category contains information about which channel of communication is tracked by which provider of altmetrics data. As D 5.1. indicated, there are different data providers in altmetrics which fulfil needs for different scholarly communities. The coverage of a specific communication may indicate as to whether the use of a communication channel relates to the needs and practices of specific scholarly communities.
- **Technical Accessibility:** Technical accessibility is meant to denote that a specific communication channel can be freely accessed through its users or by third party persons. Most usage studies in altmetrics have indicated technical accessibility through the existence of APIs (Automated Programming Interface). Some of the data relevant for studies in altmetrics, however, cannot be directly accessed but are provided by commercial services.
- **Intergenerational assessment:** The survey data have indicated that there are differences in appreciation and usage of specific communication channels. These differences may be even stronger because of a user bias towards senior scholars. This category therefore denotes as to whether the survey indicated differences.

4.3.1. Doing Science and science made public

The services which are grouped together in this dimension can be perceived as communication channels in the narrower sense, that is, their focus is primarily on communicating results or establishing attention for scholarly results. However, most of them (e.g. twitter or Facebook) have not been designed specifically for scholarly usage, but have simply become more common among scholars. On the other hand, specific services have established that imitated the structure of such services but have been developed responding to scholarly needs. Potentially, however, all of these channels can be considered as communication channels of scholars.

Table 2: Doing Science and science made public

Dimension: Doing Science and Science made public	Service 1 Blogging	Service 2 twitter	Service 3 Facebook	Service 4 RG
Attention (expert interviews, desk research)	Medium	High	High	Medium
General scholarly appreciation (Survey data)	Medium	Low	Very low	Medium
Scholarly relevance (literature review, expert interviews)	Yes	No	No	Yes
Field specific appreciation (expert interviews)	Yes	No	No	Yes
Metrics (desk research)	Citations Downloads Views	Mentions Followers	Mentions Views Likes	Activities within the network
Provider coverage (desk research)	Altmetric, Plum	Altmetric, Plum, PloS, Impactstory	Altmetric., Plum	None
Technical Accessibility (API)	Partly	Yes (but restricted)	Yes (but restricted)	No
Intergenerational differences in assessment (survey)	High	Medium	Low	NA

Structure of the tables slightly adapted from Deliverable D 5.2. of this project)

Among the assessment in the scholarly literature, scientific blogs are considered as the channels with the highest scholarly relevance; they are most similar to publications in their textual structure and the way they refer to other literature. They often provide an argument that is based on research and frequently cite other work. Different to scholarly publications however, they also aim at addressing non-scholarly audiences. Because of these reasons, blogs and sites for aggregating blogs such as ResearchBlogger are tracked by almost all altmetric providers. Referring to survey data within OpenUp, there is also some appreciation for this kind of communication. Yet it appears that there are field specific differences in usage and appreciation: Social scientists and medical scholars tend to appreciate scientific blogs more than other communities. The same can be said for the intergenerational assessment: blogs are more frequently used by junior scholars than by established professionals, as they are also more immersed in digital culture. This structure could be also revealed through the survey we conducted.

The commercial service twitter is only considered of moderate scholarly relevance, as the restriction of 140 characters does not allow for providing arguments. Nonetheless, twitter is increasingly used to promote research articles either by publishers or by scholars themselves. As a consequence, an increasing amount of tweets is related to scholarly literature. It is by far the biggest source for Altmetrics events. Thus we now have debate about as to whether twitter can be used as one of the sources for attention indicators.

Social network sites are increasingly becoming relevant for social and business life. Promotion of research thus has reached Facebook as many researchers and projects use these sites to reach their communities. Comparably to twitter, Facebook posts are rarely perceived as providing scholarly arguments but are considered to be tools for promotion. Nevertheless the appreciation of this channel

is low among the respondents of our survey. There are, however, more specific network sites for scholarly research that allow its members to connect their identity with specific highlighted content that allow them to construct specific academic network profiles. These network sites gain a lot of appreciation, maybe but not exclusively, because they (such as in the case of ResearchGate) provide metrics that enable their users to compare themselves with others in the network. However, the data for these scores only come from sources within the network and tend to incentivise activities across this site. Furthermore, the ResearchGate score appears to be rather intransparent and problematic. Finally, the data of ResearchGate events such as followers, shares, or downloads cannot be accessed freely.

4.3.2 Explaining and Entertaining

In the second group of services, explaining and entertaining, communication channels provide not only textual, but also visual, audio or audiovisual means to communicate research. The structure of contributions in these channels is different to traditional types of output. But they increasingly gain attention. The most visible and dominant source in this category is YouTube which hosts a lot of channels for scholarly topics that have many followers. YouTube is the only one which is consistently tracked and integrated in measures among the different altmetric data services.

Table 3: Explaining and Entertaining

Dimension: Explaining and Entertaining	Service 1 Youtube	Service 2 Vimeo	Service 3 Pinterest
Attention (expert interviews, desk research)	High	Medium	Low
General scholarly appreciation (Survey data)	Medium	Low	Very low
Scholarly relevance (literature review, expert interviews)	Yes	No	No
Field specific appreciation (expert interviews)	Yes	No	No
Metrics (desk research)	Followers Mentions Views	Followers Mentions	Mentions Views Likes
Provider coverage (desk research)	Altmetric, Plum	Altmetric, Plum	Altmetric., Plum
Technical Accessibility (API)	Yes	No	Yes (but restricted)
Intergenerational assessment (survey)	Medium	Low	Low

Structure of the tables slightly adapted from Deliverable D 5.2. of this project)

Given these dynamics, scholars in the field of scientometrics and informetrics tend to attribute scholarly relevance to channels like YouTube. This is different to the perception of respondents in our survey to whom YouTube appeared to be only partly relevant. But among the younger generation, there is more appreciation for YouTube which may not be fairly represented in our survey. The same goes for specific fields such as medicine or the social sciences where YouTube has become more popular in the recent years.

Popular services such as YouTube are covered by most of the altmetric providers with the exemption of PloS ALM. YouTube can be accessed and several metrics data will be available. Other channels in this group only partly provide data and are also not covered by altmetric providers. They thus play a minor role in the debate about data sources in Altmetrics.

4.3.3. Organizing attribution

In this dimension, services are grouped that provide tools for the organization of attribution. In this respect, their individual usage can be perceived as act of valuation for referring to other authors.

Reference management systems have in this way influenced the way how such attribution is organized technically and socially. Among the scholarly literature and in the expert interviews, such organization is considered to be very relevant for scholarly communication as they allow for keeping track of the vastly growing literature. In addition, they also allow to crowd resources for communities since the publications of members in the same community can be tracked. For researchers and experts in scientometrics and informetrics, reference management services like Mendeley and CiteUlike provide new and interesting insights in how scholarly output is processed and used. Most studies of cross-validation studies confirm that Mendeley has significant correlations to citations which according to some of the interviewees can almost be understood as an early indicator for citations. As a consequence, Mendeley has been most widely covered and is extensively used by scientometricians as a data source that can be linked with other meta data of scientometric importance. Other interviewees are more modest with their interpretations but agree in the relevance of these services

Table 4: Organizing attribution

Dimension: Organizing attribution	Service 1 Mendeley	Service 2 CiteUlike	Service 3 Reddit
Attention (expert interviews, desk research)	Medium	Medium	Medium
General scholarly appreciation (Survey data)	Medium	Medium	Very low
Scholarly relevance (literature review, expert interviews)	Yes	Yes	No
Field specific appreciation (expert interviews)	Yes	No	No
Metrics (desk research)	Reads Views	Reads Mentions	Mentions
Provider coverage (desk research)	Altmetric, Plum, PloS	Altmetric, Plum	Altmetric., Plum
Technical Accessibility (API)	Yes	Yes	Yes (but restricted)
Intergenerational assessment (survey)	Medium	Low	Low

Structure of the tables slightly adapted from Deliverable D 5.2. of this project)

Not only for scientometricians, but also for other scholars, metrics in Mendeley can provide meaningful data: Mendeley provides metrics that informs its users about the structure of audience a specific research item attracts. The outputs can be grouped by students, early stage, and senior scholars. All services in this category provide APIs for easy access of the data, but they are also tracked by the big altmetrics providers. By so doing, scholars can understand their readership or the readership of a specific article. The survey shows that compared to other non-traditional services, the intergenerational differences on how Mendeley is perceived are comparatively low.

4.3.4. Empowering reproducibility

The dimension 'Empowering reproducibility' groups various services that aim at enabling sharing of data or code. Comparable to the first dimension, this group consists of services that are specifically designed for scholarly demands (figshare) and others that address more diverse audiences (Github). Figshare (as part of digital science) can be considered as the one that is most specifically oriented towards scholarly audiences. Nevertheless, the services in this category are particularly used and appreciated by engineers and computer scientists who have developed a certain culture of sharing and collaborative knowledge production as our expert interviewees suggest. These kinds of tools are also appreciated by OpenScience activists as they document engagement in providing transparent access to how data were collected and algorithms were constructed. Nevertheless, the appreciation of these channels is rather low. However, publishers aim at promoting these services and encourage their authors to provide data or resources relevant for understanding how research was conducted.

Table 5: Empowering reproducibility

Dimension: Empowering reproducibility	Service 1 Github	Service 2 Figshare
Attention (expert interviews, desk research)	Low	Low
General scholarly appreciation (Survey data)	Low	Low
Scholarly relevance (literature review, expert interviews)	Some	Some
Field specific appreciation (expert interviews)	Yes	Yes
Metrics (desk research)	Shares	Shares
Provider coverage (desk research)	Altmetric, Plum, PloS	Altmetric, Plum
Technical Accessibility (API)	Yes	Yes
Intergenerational assessment (survey)	Low	Low

Structure of the tables slightly adapted from Deliverable D 5.2. of this project)

4.3.5 Stabilizing knowledge

One of the categories that are most frequently associated with knowledge transfer to non-scholarly audiences is Wikipedia. The use of Wikipedia is increasingly common among academics. Particularly in the starting phases of their research, scholars make use of this site. As a consequence, the coverage of Altmetrics events for this site increases. This does, however, not apply to other services in this group: Wikipedia is still the only source for Online Encyclopedias that is used among the main Altmetrics aggregators (Zahedi et al. 2014)

Beside such increase of use, general scholarly appreciations to this site are still rather low. Some scholars complain that their engagement in these sites is not rewarded. Interviews with altmetric service providers revealed that altmetric counts for Wikipedia are not highly rewarded because activities on this site can be easily gamed and altered. Nonetheless, the appreciation, which this source receives, has recently grown, yet is mainly triggered by science policy discourses: The expert interviews we conducted and an analysis of scholarly literature on altmetrics revealed that Wikipedia is related to a discourse about the societal impact of research. As some scholars suggested, Wikipedia entries could be used as indications of socially relevant and robust knowledge since many different authors contribute and engage in discussions. There have been opposing views in our interviews towards this claim but the debate has certainly attributed some kind of attention to Wikipedia as a source for altmetrics. There are differences as to whether Wikipedia is appreciated among the various fields and communities, as Wikipedia has become most important in the natural and life sciences. Increasingly Wikipedia is also appreciated by social scientists and the humanities.

Table 5: Stabilizing knowledge

Dimension: Stabilizing knowledge	Service 1 Wikipedia
Attention	Medium
General scholarly appreciation (Survey data)	Medium

Scholarly relevance (literature review, expert interviews)	Yes
Field specific appreciation (expert interviews)	No
Metrics (desk research)	Contributions
Provider coverage (desk research)	Altmetric, Plum, PloS
Technical Accessibility (API)	Yes
Intergenerational assessment (survey)	Medium

(Structure of the tables slightly adapted from Deliverable D 5.2. of this project)

4.3.6. Supporting policy

Policy papers have more recently become a more relevant source for analysing the way how scholarly output travels to non-scholarly audiences. There are no specific channels or service that collects such documents, but policy papers have been introduced as a new data source for mentions of scholarly work by. Again mentions to these documents are related to debates about the societal impact of research since particularly output from the social sciences are taken up by policy makers and are thus listed in the reference list of policy documents. Policy documents in this view would document the engagement of scholars in policy debates and the attention a scholarly output generates in this field. Nonetheless, the appreciation which such kind of transfer generates differs since in some communities, translations to policy are perceived as biasing research results.

In addition, there are various problems with policy documents as a source for mentions since it is not to easy to achieve substantial coverage of such documents, particularly if they are not in English as most of the text-mining tools for identification are designed for the English language. As a consequence, scholars should be aware of these problems and cautious with metrics to these documents.

Table 6: Supporting policy

Dimension: Supporting policy	Service 1 Policy documents
Attention (expert interviews, desk research)	Medium
General scholarly appreciation (Survey data)	Medium
Scholarly relevance (literature review, expert interviews)	NA
Field specific appreciation (expert interviews)	Yes
Metrics (desk research)	Citations, contributions
Provider coverage (desk research)	Altmetric
Technical Accessibility (API)	No
Intergenerational assessment (survey)	High

(Structure of the tables slightly adapted from Deliverable D 5.2. of this project)

4.4. A route towards interpreting mechanisms between channels of dissemination and Altmetrics:

Through these various activities of reviewing literature, surveying the research community and the insights of the experts, we are in the position of providing insight in how one might understand mechanisms for the dynamics in the channel of dissemination and how they are linked to novel metrics currently labelled as Altmetrics. As outlined above, we can distinguish between those processes that drive the appreciation and valuation of novel channels of communication, the processes that drives the production of metrics and those processes that reflect mutual relationships between the two different forces. It should be mentioned, however, that the processes which are portrayed here should be interpreted with caution since the general appreciation of these novel communication and ultimately their quantification appears to be only appreciated to lesser extent by the scholarly community as our analyses indicate. As outlined in the presentation of expert opinions, the perception of communication channels is largely driven by the incentives of the scholarly reward system which is increasingly putting pressure on scientists. Since the meaning and incentive structure of novel communication channels are not easy to understand, many scientist stick to established communication channels such as publications and conferences.

After this general remark of how the analysis should be contextualised, following processes can be identified: First on the side of communication channels, we have specific media inherent values that structure their appreciation. That is, different functions which they provide for specific purposes such as organizing attribution, entertaining, organizing debates and science made public (blogs, microblogs), integrating the stock of knowledge and various others. These values greatly influence how these channels are perceived. In the previous report, we have argued that the way these channels are attributed value is through both their use and consumption.

However, as our survey indicates, the perception of these channels differs between various fields and communities. While for instance, in the social sciences and the humanities, the organization of public debates and the popularization of scholarly knowledge are highly valued, the same does not account for some of the natural sciences. As a consequence for instance, we can observe strong differences in how blogs or microblogs are perceived among these fields. On the other hand, communities can thrive for making their specific output more visible as they intend to become more influential among funders and policy makers. As we have argued above, there are some mechanisms that can make these channels more valuable. Specific discourses, for instance can contribute to a valuation of specific communication channels. Two of these discourses have been identified to be highly relevant for the perception and valuation of channels of communication that is, the discourse about societal impact as well as the discourse about research performance. Both of these discourses can be found in scholarly as well as in political debates. As our expert interviews revealed assumptions related to these discourses widely shared and can be used as legitimizing resource in various ways.

Second, on the other hand, we can elaborate on specific processes that appear to drive the practices of metric construction. Initially, one of the forces was the dissatisfaction with traditional research evaluation and with established indicators for their use. The metric construction is therefore first of all driven by the force of finding more and more telling data for informing or assessing about research output. Increasingly, however, this dynamic has been more strongly transformed by technical considerations. With the proliferation of data sources on any kind of communication, new possibilities for relating scholarly output to new communication channels arise. As it becomes easier to harvest digital data sources, attempts for systematic conceptual scrutinization of which data to be used becomes less important. In this way technical opportunities become a major force for metrification. Along with these metrifications of many different data sources and their integration in composite indicators, it increasingly becomes unclear how each communication channel is represented and what the metrics mean to its users. Therefore, the contextualization with established indicators will grow in the foreseeable future.

Finally we can observe accounts that seem to indicate the prevalence of mutual processes between communication and metrification. One of these mechanisms has been elaborated above as the

categorization and classification practices on the metric provider and the valuation acts as recipients and producers at the scholarly side. Furthermore, we see new infrastructural processes that link to both of these sides. There is an increasing need of self-administration and communication due to an accelerated demands and expectations by societal audiences. This leads to new ecosystems of metadata and landscapes of data which served by academic services providers. These fast growing ecosystems are highly directly tied to both worlds: the world of scholarly services and the world of academic metric provider. Sources like ORCID increasingly populate digital platforms for science and become important. At the same, we can observe how community building of scholarly communities and outreach activities of services and metric provider mutually reinforce each other: As communities increasingly attempt to find new ways to gather and aggregate research in new ways so as to generate and channel attention to specific objects of science, outreach activities of service providers who search for new data sources become more aware of specific kinds of scholarly output promoted by specific communities. A good example is the case on clinical trials in the US which has been driven by the idea of receiving credit for a specific kind of research. This motivation somehow has been met the outreach activities of altmetric.com who seek to integrate different perspectives on which channels to integrate. Finally, the altmetric providers develop new categories and classifications in which data sources are aggregated and collected in such a way that manipulation and misuse is only integrated.

5. Conclusion and outlook

Our goal in this report was to provide a taxonomy that links innovative channels of dissemination with alternative or open metrics. We have done so, first, by providing a framework for construction based on the theoretical approach of the sociology of valuation. We have identified different media inherent valuations of novel dissemination channels. Their appreciation, however, also rests on practices of classification, evaluation, and communicability that further specify the relevance of a communication channel. In order to further develop these categories, we provided a methodology linking various sources and activities that can enrich and deepen our taxonomy, e.g., analysis of scholarly literature, secondary analysis of survey, expert interviews, and the mapping of metrics.

Second, we have provided results that have been carved out from these various activities. Thereby, we can establish that our taxonomy can be perceived as empirically grounded. The qualitative expert interviews allowed for developing further categories that enriched our taxonomy. In particular, we could observe how material and technical attributes constrained but also enabled the construction of metrics for specific channels of communication which subsequently also influence the use of these channels. On the other hand, the results of the survey allowed for specifying the general appreciation novel dissemination channels receive and the more general awareness in the scholarly realm. The results from the survey show that established channels of scholarly communication are perceived as most relevant and useful. Innovative dissemination channels, on which this report is focused on, are still only of minor significance. One of the reasons why new practices have not been taken up are deeply entrenched reward systems which are linked to contemporary regimes of evaluation. It remains unclear so far whether a new regime of evaluation is emerging. Nevertheless, the survey results allow for making claims about the general appreciation of a communication channel.

Linking this information to the output from our analysis of the scholarly debate (Deliverable D 5.1), we were able to construct and specify a taxonomy for each group of dissemination channels. The results show the different communication channels vary in the degree they are appreciated but also covered by altmetric providers. Nonetheless, we could see a close relation between altmetrics coverage and scholarly appreciation. The analysis reveals that more efforts are needed to make the data more meaningful. This would imply more efforts for data integration or contextualization. The different stakeholders, publishers, scholars, policy makers, and service providers will need to collaborate in order to improve the concepts of Altmetrics.

This report has tried to provide some background information on how these metrics can be used and interpreted for scholarly and non-scholarly audiences. Through the above mentioned activities, we were able to define a taxonomy of channels of dissemination with Altmetrics. Different dimensions for

scholarly communication and collaboration that group several services have been provided and further specific by specific categories of their appreciation, valuation, and implementation. Some of them have slightly changed in comparison to the interim report since new categories have emerged during the course of conducting interviews.

Finally, our goal with this taxonomy is to inform and orient strategies of scholarly dissemination strategies. We hope that the derived taxonomy might also stimulate debate about the uses and problems with innovative channels of dissemination and their current counting practices. We are also aware that, by providing this information, our taxonomy will lend visibility and credibility to some of the channels and services presented here. We hope the taxonomy and the specifications finally provided therein can be used as a resource for reflection of these recent developments.

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Appendix A: Corpus of scholarly literature on innovative dissemination channels and altmetrics

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Appendix B Survey Questionnaire

1. Introduction

1.1. What is the core scientific discipline of your research?

Natural Sciences	
Engineering and Technology	
Medical Sciences	
Agricultural Sciences	
Social Sciences	
Humanities	
Other (please specify):	

1.2. Which stage of your career are you at?

First Stage Researcher (doctoral candidate stage or equivalent, without having undertaken a doctorate)	
Recognized Researcher (PhD holder or equivalent who is not yet fully independent; non-tenured assistant professor; post-doctoral stage)	
Established Researcher (researcher who has developed a level of independence; tenured assistant or associate professor; research specialist or manager, senior lecturer, senior scientist)	
Leading Researcher (researcher leading his/her research area or field; professor stage)	

1.3. What is your gender?

Male	
Female	
Prefer not to say	
Other	

1.4. What type of organisation do you currently work for? If you work for more than one organisation, please choose the one you consider to be your main employer.

University	
Research centre/institute	
Company	
Other type of organisation (please specify)	
Do not know/cannot answer	

1.4.a. What is the sector of this organisation?

Public or government sector	
Private, not-for-profit sector	
Private for-profit	
Other (please specify)	
Do not know/cannot answer	

1.5. How important to you are the research outputs listed below?

By important we mean the outputs which you produce most frequently, or outputs upon which your success as a researcher mostly relies on.

	Very important	Somewhat important	Neither important nor not important	Somewhat unimportant	Not important at all	Do not know / cannot answer
Peer-reviewed publications						
Books, book chapters, monographs						
Data, datasets (i.e. as primary output/goal of your research activities)						
Software, IT tools and applications						
Intellectual property rights (patents, trademarks, utility designs, etc.)						
Protocols, ontologies, guidelines, methodologies for practitioners						
Policy outputs (e.g. policy conclusions and recommendations, reports, briefs, etc.)						
Other research outputs (please specify)						

2. Peer review process

Peer review is a process in which qualified scientific experts (peers) scrutinise the research results and assess if they are valid, significant and original, and whether they can be published in a scholarly journal. Traditional/established peer review includes two review formats, including single-blind and double-blind review. The reviewer's identity is concealed in both cases, however the author's identity can either be known to the reviewer (single-blind review), or be concealed as well (double-blind review).

Open peer review (OPR) introduces a variety of innovations to the traditional peer review process. Primary aspects of OPR are: (1) Open Identities: authors and reviewers are aware of each other's identity; (2) Open Reports: review reports are published alongside the relevant article; and (3) Open Participation: the wider community to able to contribute to the review process.

2.1. Do you have prior experience as the main author of at least one peer-reviewed publication?

Yes	
No	Filter to 2.2

2.1.a [if have experience as an author in 2.1]: Considering your overall experience as an author, how satisfied are you with the established peer review process?

Very satisfied	
Somewhat satisfied	
Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	
Somewhat dissatisfied	

Very dissatisfied	
Do not know / cannot answer	

2.1.b. [if answered neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, somewhat dissatisfied or very dissatisfied in 2.1.a]: You have indicated a low or neutral overall satisfaction with the established peer review process in the previous question. How important are the reasons listed below behind your reservations with the established peer review system?

	Very important	Somewhat important	Neither important nor not important	Somewhat unimportant	Not important at all	Do not know / cannot answer
Quality of peer review reports						
Time/duration peer review takes						
Transparency issues, i.e. lack of openness in the process						
Lack of scientific communication between authors and reviewers						
Other reasons (please specify)						

2.1.c [if have experience as an author in 2.1] Which of the following peer review approaches would you choose to undergo for your own research outputs?

The approaches described on the left refer to open peer review approaches, while the ones on the right are practices which tend to occur under the currently established system. Please answer this question assuming that your own research outputs would have to undergo the peer review approaches described below.

	Strongly support open peer review	Rather in support of open peer review	Indifferent between the approaches	Rather in support of the established peer review	Strongly support the established peer review	
Open report: review report is published alongside the relevant article						Closed report: no review report is published alongside the relevant article
Open identity: authors and reviewers are aware of each other's identity						Closed identity: neither the author's nor the reviewer's identity are disclosed
Open participation: a wider community of researchers contributes to peer review						Closed participation: only appointed peer reviewers contribute to peer review

Open platform: peer review is managed by a different organisation than the publishing body						Peer review is managed by the publishing body
Open pre-review: manuscripts are made available to researchers/public before formal peer review						No open pre-review: manuscripts are not made available to researchers/public before formal peer review
Open final-version commenting: review/commenting after publication						No final-version commenting after publication
Data review: datasets used/produced are accessible and reviewed along with the paper						No data review: accessible datasets typically are not reviewed along with the paper

2.1.d [if have experience as an author in 2.1] How frequently do you make your key research outputs openly accessible and free of charge to use?

	Always, or almost always (90-100% of the time)	Most of the time (60-89% of the time)	Sometimes (40-59% of the time)	Rarely (11-39% of the time)	Never, or almost never (0-10% of the time)	Do not know / cannot answer
Scientific publications						
Books, book chapters, monographs						
Data, datasets (i.e. as primary output/goal of your research activities)						
Software, IT tools and applications						
Protocols, ontologies, guidelines, methodologies for practitioners						
Policy outputs (e.g. policy conclusions and recommendations)						
Other types of outputs (please specify)						

2.1.e. [if have experience as an author in 2.1] To what extent do these factors/barriers prevent you from making more of your research results openly accessible and free of charge to use?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To little or no extent at all	Do not know / cannot answer
Negative personal perceptions about open access					
My organisation encourages me to publish in traditional outlets/journals which have restricted access					
By publishing in open access outlets/journals I would likely negatively affect my career development and performance assessment in my organisation					
Lack of financial support to openly share my research results					
Lack of knowledge about open access platforms and services where my research results could be published					
Privacy and/or ethical concerns					
Other factors/barriers (please specify)					

2.2 Do you have prior experience as a reviewer of at least one peer-reviewed publication?

Yes	
No	Filter to 3.1

2.2.a. [if have experience as a reviewer in 2.2] To what extent do you agree with these statements considering your experience as a reviewer under the established peer review system?

	Strongly agree	Rather agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Rather disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know / cannot answer
My work as a reviewer is being explicitly acknowledged and evaluated in my organisation						
My work as a reviewer benefits my career development						
My incentives to work as a reviewer would increase if my review comments were published under my name						

My incentives to work as a reviewer would increase if my review work was remunerated						
My incentives to work as a reviewer would increase if the peer review process became more collaborative with authors, editors and/or publishers						

Dissemination of research results

For the purposes of this survey, we define dissemination as follows:

Dissemination is a planned process that involves consideration of target audiences and the settings in which research findings will be shared. Where appropriate, dissemination involves communicating and interacting with wider audiences to facilitate research uptake in decision-making processes and practice.

3.1. How important is the dissemination of research results to non-research audiences (e.g. practitioners, citizens, journalists, policymakers, industry, etc.) in your specific research area?

Very important	
Rather important	
Neither important nor unimportant	
Rather unimportant	
Not important at all	
Do not know / cannot answer	

3.2. How often do you target the following audiences when disseminating your research findings?

	Always, or almost always (90-100% of the time)	Most of the time (60-89% of the time)	Sometimes (40-59% of the time)	Rarely (11-39% of the time)	Never, or almost never (0-10% of the time)	Do not know / cannot answer
Researchers from my own discipline/area						
Researchers from other disciplines/areas						
Teachers						
Students						
Policy makers & government						
Practitioners						
Industry/business						
General public						
Journalists						
Charities/NGOs						
Children up to the age of 14						
Other (please specify)	free text box					

3.3. When do you usually start disseminating your research?

During the initial/inception phase of the research activities (i.e. shortly before or after the start of your research projects)	
During the main phase of the research activities (e.g. during data collection; field research, etc.);	
After conclusion of the research activities (i.e. end of project, publication of research results, etc.)	
Do not know/cannot answer	

3.4. How important are the following reasons when disseminating the findings of your research?

	Very important	Somewhat important	Neither important nor unimportant	Somewhat unimportant	Not important at all	Do not know / cannot answer
Contributing to the body of knowledge, enabling other researchers to build on top of my research						
Raising awareness of the findings						
Stimulating discussions and public understanding of science						
Receiving feedback on my research						
Influencing policymaking and practices by transferring my research results						
Justifying public funding of my research						
Attracting future funding						
Raising my own or my organisation's profile						
Dissemination is part of my performance assessments/evaluations in my organisation						
Improving my communication skills						
Satisfying contractual obligations (e.g. research funding)						
Other (Specify)						

3.5. Which of these channels listed do you use most frequently to disseminate your own research to reach your target groups?

	Always, or almost always (90-100% of the time)	Most of the time (60-89% of the time)	Sometimes (40-59% of the time)	Rarely (11-39% of the time)	Never, or almost never (0-10% of the time)	Do not know/cannot answer

Traditional academic publishing (e.g. academic journals, books)						
Popular science publications (e.g. magazines)						
Academic conferences/workshops						
Events for the general public/specific target audiences other than researchers						
Press releases						
Television/radio programs						
Open access repositories/ preprint servers (e.g. Zenodo, arXiv)						
Academic social networks (e.g. ResearchGate, Academia.edu)						
Non-specialist social networks (e.g. Facebook, Twitter)						
Podcasts, Video sharing sites (e.g. YouTube, Vimeo)						
Wikipedia						
Blogs, other wikis (excluding Wikipedia)						
E-Mail/Newsletters						
Personal/Project Website						
Open lab books/interactive notebooks						
Print media (e.g. leaflets, folders)						
Git repositories (e.g. GitHub)						
Exhibitions, performances						
Other (please specify)						

3.6. And how frequently do you use these sources to inform your professional work as a researcher?

	Always, or almost always (90-100% of the time)	Most of the time (60-89% of the time)	Sometimes (40-59% of the time)	Rarely (11-39% of the time)	Never, or almost never (0-10% of the time)	Do not know/cannot answer
Traditional academic publishing (e.g. academic journals, books)						
Popular science publications (e.g. magazines)						
Academic conferences/workshops						
Events for the general public/specific target audiences other than researchers						
Press releases						
Television/radio programs						
Open access repositories/ preprint servers (e.g. Zenodo, arXiv)						
Academic social networks (e.g. ResearchGate, Academia.edu)						
Non-specialist social networks (e.g. Facebook, Twitter)						

Podcasts, Video sharing sites (e.g. YouTube)						
Wikipedia						
Blogs, other wikis (excluding Wikipedia)						
E-Mail/Newsletters						
Personal/Project Website						
Open lab books/interactive notebooks						
Print media (e.g. leaflets, folders)						
Git repositories (e.g. GitHub)						
Exhibitions, performances						
Other (please specify)						

3.7. Have you achieved any outstanding results by disseminating your research through dissemination channels other than traditional academic publishing, conferences and workshops in the past 5 years?

Yes
No

3.7.a [if answered yes]: Could you briefly describe your method and the success achieved? (open text)

Yes
In case of Yes: could you briefly describe your method and the success achieved?

3.7.b [if answered yes]: Would you agree if we contacted you via email for more details on your success story?

Yes
In case of Yes: could you briefly describe your method and the success achieved?
No

3.8. To what extent do you agree with the following statement: my research results successfully reach the key target groups

To a very large extent	
To a large extent	
To some extent	
To little or no extent at all	
Do not know / cannot answer	

3.8.a. To what extent do these factors prevent you from disseminating your results more effectively through non-traditional dissemination channels?

By non-traditional dissemination channels we mean channels other than traditional academic publishing (e.g. academic journals, books, monographs), conferences and workshops

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To little or no extent at all	Do not know / cannot answer
I do not need non-traditional dissemination to reach my target audiences.					
Time constraints					
Lack of financial support for non-traditional dissemination					
Lack of acknowledgement/credit given to non-traditional dissemination in my research field					
Lack of organizational support for non-traditional dissemination					
Lack of knowledge about non-traditional dissemination tools and methods					

Lack of presentation and communication skills					
Missing IT infrastructure					
Privacy and/or ethical concerns					
Legal/contractual barriers					
Other factors (please specify)					

3. Altmetrics & perceptions about dissemination channels

In the recent years “alternative metrics” or altmetrics have become a topic in the debate about a balanced assessment of research efforts as a complementary way of assessment beyond publication output and measures of reception via citation counts of peer-reviewed articles.

In the following section we want to assess, if such alternative metrics have become an important issue in your own work and your research field as a whole. In addition, we ask questions about the perceptions and potential of the different dissemination channels in your specific research area.

4.1. Are you aware of the term “alternative metrics” (altmetrics)?

Yes	
No	Filter to IV.4

4.1.a. Have you ever used alternative metrics in your work (e.g. to learn more about your own research profile or achievements, follow other researchers, find interesting research, etc.)?

Yes	
No	Filter to IV.3

4.2. To what extent do these statements apply to you?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To little or no extent at all	Do not know / cannot answer
I actively follow the development of alternative metric scores of my research					
I take measures to increase my alternative metrics scores					
I use alternative metrics to compare myself to other researchers					
I take alternative metrics into account when identifying interesting research					
I think that alternative metrics have an effect on how I am perceived as a researcher by others in my field of research					
Performance evaluations including alternative metrics would assess the achievements of my research in a more balanced way.					

4.3. To what extent do these factors prevent you from using alternative metrics in your work more actively?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To little or no extent at all	Do not know / cannot answer

Lack of overall awareness of alternative metrics and their meaning/value in my organisation					
Lack of training on how to optimise my altmetrics scores					
Lack of awareness of tools and approaches which can show my altmetrics scores					
Lack of understanding of how alternative metrics scores are calculated and can be interpreted					
Other factors (please specify)					

4.4. Please rate how being represented in these dissemination activities is generally appreciated within your field of research (i.e. by your academic peers or organisation which employs you)

	Very appreciated	Moderately appreciated	Neither appreciated nor underappreciated	Moderately underappreciated	Not appreciated at all	Do not know/cannot answer
Traditional academic publishing (e.g. academic journals, books)						
Popular science publications						
Academic conferences/workshops						
Events for the general public/specific target audiences other than researchers						
Press releases						
Television/radio programs						
Open access repositories/ preprint servers (e.g. Zenodo, arXiv)						
Academic social networks (e.g. ResearchGate, Academia.edu)						
Non-specialist social networks (e.g. Facebook, Twitter)						
Podcasts, Video sharing sites (e.g. YouTube, Vimeo)						
Wikipedia						
Blogs, other wikis (excluding Wikipedia)						
E-Mail/Newsletters						
Personal/Project Website						

Open lab books/interactive notebooks						
Print media (e.g. leaflets, folders)						
Git repositories (e.g. GitHub)						
Exhibitions, performances						
Other (please specify)						

4.5. Finally, what potential do the following dissemination channels have to lead to a wider societal impact?

	Very high potential	High potential	Some potential	Little or no potential	Do not know / cannot answer
Traditional academic publishing (e.g. academic journals, books)					
Popular science publications					
Academic conferences/workshops					
Events for the general public/specific target audiences other than researchers					
Press releases					
Television/radio programs					
Open access repositories/preprint servers (e.g. Zenodo, arXiv)					
Academic social networks (e.g. ResearchGate, Academia.edu)					
Non-specialist social networks (e.g. Facebook, Twitter)					
Podcasts, Video sharing sites (e.g. YouTube)					
Wikipedia					
Blogs, other wikis (excluding Wikipedia)					
E-Mail/Newsletters					
Personal/Project Website					
Open lab books/interactive notebooks					
Print media (e.g. leaflets, folders)					
Git repositories (e.g. GitHub)					
Exhibitions, performances					
Other (please specify)					

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ANSWERS!

Appendix C Approached List of Expert Interviewees

ID	IID	Author Fullname	Organization	Country
73	1	Thelwall, Mike	Wolverhampton Univ	ENGLAND
22	2a	Bornmann, Lutz	Max Planck Gesell	GERMANY
	2b	McCallum, Catriona	Hindawi Publishers	ENGLAND
42 2	3	Lariviere, Vincent	Univ Montreal	CANADA
17 0	4	Peters, Isabella	ZBW Leibniz Informat Ctr Econ	GERMANY
41 9	5	Holmberg, Kim	Univ Turku	FINLAND
17 4	6	Gorraiz, Juan	Univ Vienna	AUSTRIA
49 0	7	Costas, Rodrigo	Leiden Univ	NETHERLAND S
42 1	8	Sugimoto, Cassidy	Indiana Univ	USA
57 4	9	Torres-Salinas, Daniel	Univ Navarra	SPAIN
33 4	10	Moed, Henk F.	Elsevier	NETHERLAND S
49 2	11	Wouters, Paul	Leiden Univ	NETHERLAND S
59 7	12	Bar-Ilan, Judit	Bar Ilan Univ	ISRAEL

80	13	Glanzel, Wolfgang	Katholieke Univ Leuven	BELGIUM
17 2	14	Lex, Elisabeth	Graz Univ Technol	AUSTRIA
75 4	15	Priem, Jason	Altmetric.com	USA
16 5	16	Ingwersen, Peter	Univ Copenhagen	DENMARK
	17	Büttgen, Stephan	Plum Analytics	
	18		ResearchGate	GERMANY
	19		Thomson Reuters	UK
	20	Price, Richard	Academia.edu	UK
	21	Wilsdon, James	University of Sheffield (also Altmetric.com)	UK
	22	Piwowar, Heather	Impactstory	USA
	23	Vaughan, Liwen	University of Ontario	USA
	24	Neylon, Cameron	Curtin University	AUSTRALIA
	25	Cronin, Blaise	Indiana University	USA
	26	Attenborough	PloS One	UK
ID	Records	Author Fullname	Organizations	Country
81	27	Haustein, Stefanie	Univ Montreal	CANADA
17 8	28	Kousha, Kayvan	Wolverhampton Univ	ENGLAND

72	29	Haunschild, Robin	Max Planck Inst Solid State Res	GERMANY
418	30	Bowman, Timothy D.	Univ Montreal	CANADA
173	31	Gumpenberger, Christian	Univ Vienna	AUSTRIA
481	32	Fairclough, Ruth	Wolverhampton Univ	ENGLAND
211	33	Eysenbach, Gunther	TrendMD Inc	CANADA
88	34	Tattersall, Andy	SCHARR	ENGLAND
	34	Groth, Paul	Elsevier	NETHERLANDS
	35	Garfinkel, Michele	EMBO Journal, OSPP	GERMANY, USA
	36	Berghans, Stephan	ELSEVIER	NETHERLANDS
	37	Tochtermann, Klaus	ZBW, OSPP	GERMANY
	38	Matteo Razzanelli	Policy Adviser at European Research Council	BELGIUM
	39	Marco Malgarini	Senior Manager for Research Evaluation	BELGIUM
	40	Thomas Jørgensen	European University Association, Senior Policy Coordinator,	BELGIUM
	41	Harriman, Stephanie	Editor at BioMed Central	UK
	42	Dawson, Stephanie	CEO Science Open Platform	Germany
	43	Wille, Eva	Wiley VCH	USA

Appendix D: Interview Guideline: Innovative Channels of Dissemination and Altmetrics

- 1) As a short intro: Do you use innovative channels of dissemination (social media tools, open science tools, non-scholarly resources) to communicate your research?
- 2) Do you use Altmetrics on your own (for comparing your research with others or to increase visibility), for any other specific purpose)?
- 3) According to your perception, how are these channels used in your specific field of research? How are metrics that build upon these channels used?
- 4) Do you think there are specific choices/challenges of Altmetrics usage?

General Assessment and Perception of Dissemination Channels and Altmetrics

- 5) In more general terms, how do you perceive the Altmetrics movement (is it a hype, a new discipline, or community, or simply a new topic for scholars), what is it in your terms?
- 6) What are the main drivers/actors in diffusing Altmetrics in research and practice?
- 7) When reflecting about these descriptions, do you think you have a specific perspective towards Altmetrics? Could you describe that in more detail?

Data sources

- 8) There are now various providers for social media use and Altmetrics: Which of them do you consider most relevant (according to your field, your experience, from a more general stance)?
- 9) Altmetrics providers use many different data sources: Which are most relevant and why?
- 10) How do these different channels of dissemination become relevant and more visible?
- 11) As a scholar, on what basis should I decide how to use these data sources?
- 12) How do you perceive the way data sources in Altmetrics are aggregated and collected - are there any systematic problems or choices?
- 13) How do you perceive the role of these platform providers in Altmetrics? Will they have an impact on how data are collected?

Evaluation and Impact Assessment

- 14) Currently, there is a dominant debate that relates the use of innovative channels of dissemination to research performance and impact measurement. From your perspective as an expert in the field, is there an influence of Altmetrics on measuring research impact or research performance? How would you describe such influence?
- 15) Does this debate change the way innovative channels of dissemination are perceived?
- 16) What else can be said about the relationships to scientometrics, bibliometrics, and librarianship if any?
- 17) Can Altmetrics research contribute to scientometrics and evaluative bibliometrics?
- 18) Currently, some scholars use the phrase of “societal impact” to circumscribe the impact Altmetrics can have on other, non-scholarly audiences? What is your perception towards this topic?

Public Understanding of Altmetrics

- 19) How would you describe the public understanding and societal debate of Altmetrics
- 20) There is also the perception of Altmetrics propagators that it can help to make science more open and transparent? What do you think about these claims and expectations?

Appendix E: Documentation of Workshop results

Documentation and Validation of taxonomy results in a workshop

In order to discuss the research with and to gather additional input for the development of the taxonomy linking dissemination and Altmetrics in WP5, we conducted two workshops. These workshops have been conducted during and before the Open Science Conference in Berlin which took place in March 2017. The workshops have been designed and coproduced by collaborators and WPL in WP 4. Michela Vignola and Peter Kraker have been significantly contributed in documenting and analysing workshop results.

General information about the participants and the setting of the workshops

Attendance to both workshops was limited due to location constraints; approx. 20-25 participants attended each of the workshops. The workshops complemented each other regarding attendance and involvement of different stakeholders. While the Barcamp featured stakeholders from the group of researchers, students, and open science activists, the main stakeholders attending the OSC2017 workshop were research funders, policy makers, publishers, and a smaller number of researchers. Both workshops differed in their setup while sharing a common approach towards presenting the overall objectives of OpenUP, the state of the field of Altmetrics, as well as current strands of research and thematic orientation within Altmetrics research. In addition, the workshops featured an assessment of future challenges within Altmetrics and results of the analyses of the OpenUP survey conducted in the context of WP7. The OSC2017 workshop included all content from the Barcamp workshop but went beyond the scope of the Barcamp session by presenting a more detailed set of results of WP4.

Summary of the Barcamp Workshop

In order to leverage the impact of OpenUP and to get additional input from this stakeholder group, the WP5 team decided to host a session with participants at the Barcamp in order to get additional input from this stakeholder group. There were about 18 participants (including the organisers).

The OpenUP team provided a short input of the landscape, practices and perceptions towards altmetrics. The participants were then requested to provide their perceptions and personal involvement. Generally, most participants are aware of the Altmetrics term. Yet, few participants have actively engaged in the subject or used these metrics for self-tracking or as means to signal their actions towards others. One major issue of discussion was the relationship between Altmetrics and quality assurance. Most attendants were skeptical towards Altmetrics reflecting a quality dimension as such. Regarding the assessment of impact, the discussion was diverse with two major opposing positions towards Altmetrics either measuring societal impact or attention. Most attendants sided with the modest assessment of Altmetrics reflecting attention rather than impact. Discussion revolved around questions that relate to the content-perspective as well as the motivational aspect of social media communication vis-à-vis deducing an impact, e.g. “Why is a paper tweeted?” or “Who is tweeting about it?”. Yet, selected attendants also argued that despite the shortcomings of the indicators to capture societal impact, it should be considered as “the next best thing that we have coming close to it”. All participants agreed that Altmetrics provide a filter for information that seems to have some merit in terms of personal information collection strategies. Yet, some participants argued that, depending on previously unknown mechanisms and in-transparent indicator calculation, the threat of a “filter bubble” might lead to a shift in attention towards certain academic outputs. The features therein are yet to be determined through analyses of the previously discussed aspects.

Reservations towards Altmetrics were discussed regarding their inclusion as a reward mechanism within a science policy context. The overall conclusion was that currently the state of the art is too shallow to support actions to this end, especially when including such metrics in context of funding decisions. Regarding evaluation, the opinions ranged from support and reservations to include such metrics in the assessment of dissemination. In this context attendants also argued that the current expectations towards Altmetrics in terms of their validity, reliability, and conceptual coverage from policy makers is too high, potentially leading to hasty implementation of such metrics.

Comparing Altmetrics with established indicators of research impact, the participants agreed that the relationship between both is at best complementary. Substitution of established metrics in favor of Altmetrics-only approaches was deemed as unsuitable.

Summary of the OSC2017 Workshop

The OSC2017 workshop took place at the first day of the conference. Attendance included a wide variety of stakeholders ranging from interested researchers to high level policy makers. We saw a high interest in the workshop: total attendance in the workshop was above 25 , which meant that every last seat in the conference room was filled, and we even had to turn people away. The final discussion was recorded as audio for internal and evaluative purposes, yet is not deemed to be released publicly. Overall, the workshop was very well received by the attendants.

In contrast to the workshop at the Barcamp event, the workshop at OSC2017 included a 4-stage interactive task to collect, operationalize, and reflect on the relationship between channels of innovative dissemination and Altmetrics. As the workshop at OSC was to a large extent attended by policy makers and non-researcher stakeholders the initial focus on dissemination channels used by the stakeholders themselves was re-formulated to reflect innovative channels as they were deemed most interesting, relevant, and innovative from both the perspective of provision of content through dissemination as well as from the perspective of recipients of such means of innovative dissemination. In contrast to the workshop at the Wikimedia Barcamp an overview was provided of the ten case studies produced in WP4. The four tasks were:

- Stage 1: Collect. What are the most innovative dissemination channels you have used recently?
- Stage 2: Assign. What do others think about how much these channels facilitate impact?
- Stage 3: Measure. How do you think this value might be translated to indicators?
- Stage 4: Reflect. How do you think such measures will influence how the work of researchers and the science system progress?

Attendants were provided with cards of different color and markers and were requested give written input about important innovative channels of dissemination in stage 1. In the second stage, attendants had to assess the importance of the channels of dissemination that have been pinned on the board. In stage 3, attendants were requested to develop ideas for metrics for all the dissemination channels. In stage 4, the results from stage 1-3 were taken into account and discussed with the audience to deduct potential overarching conclusions on potentials, reservations and challenges of innovative dissemination channels. During the intermissions between the four tasks selected cases from WP4 were presented in detail to make the audience aware of innovative dissemination activities. This also provided the opportunity to process the input by the audience between each stage, and to prepare and consolidate the content to address subsequent tasks.

In the remainder of this summary, the results of these tasks will be described in brief.

Stage 1 (Collect. What are the most innovative dissemination channels you have used recently?)

In general, most of the attendants selected services from the domain of social networks as interesting and innovative dissemination channel. Both academic as well as generic social networks were mentioned by the attendants. Overall, Twitter received by far the most mentions. Second most mentioned channels were video platforms, such as YouTube. Other channels mainly were oriented towards Open Education such as Webinars and MOOCs. Interestingly, attendants also mentioned localized events as innovative dissemination channels such as Science Slams or Science Cafes.

Prior to stage 2, cards were clustered into groups and duplicate cards were removed. This allowed for an easier assessment in the later stages.

Stage 2: Assign. What do others think about how much these channels facilitate impact?

The public vote mainly reflected the initial collection of duplicates in channels. In this round, YouTube received by far the most votes, followed by Research Gate and other channels (Mendeley, Twitter, Podcast, Webinars, Broadcasting, and GitHub).

Prior to stage 3, the results of the assessment was visualized by ordering the cards according to the assessment number of points they had received, taking into account the individual cluster structure as produced prior to stage 2. This resulted in a matrix with clusters as columns and hierarchical sorting as vertical position within these columns.

Stage 3: Measure. How do you think this value might be translated to indicators?

In this round, participants were asked to provide further input relative to how interesting dissemination channels could be transformed into metrics to capture impact and benefits of these channels. Most input related to attempting to capture diverse forms of actions by users of the services. One example for this was the suggestion to count commits and activities on GitHub to evaluate software produced in research projects. Similar suggestions related to the usual modes of appreciation provided by services themselves, such as likes, up-votes, etc. as well as sharing.

Interestingly, some participants introduced notions that are closely related to discussions familiar in bibliometrics, i.e. the differentiation between quality, importance and impact. Impact in this regard is a resulting success term, which can only be judged from effects of an action towards wider implications. In this respect, participants argued that impact reflects change of behavior and cognition resulting from scholarly communication via social media. Other participants highlighted the connected nature of impact assessment, which has also been discussed in the Altmetrics community through means of cross-validation studies, e.g. correlating one established metric with a newly constructed one.

Stage 4: Reflect. How do you think such measures will influence how the work of researchers and the science system progress?

In the final stage, the participants were asked to write down measures or approaches on how to translate the impact generated into indicators, and to pin down the identified measures next to the individual channels. For example, one suggestion given was to correlate Mendeley data with citations.

In a final reflection round, the participants discussed how such measures would influence how research work is done and how it is disseminated. Many interesting points were touched upon. For instance, it was discussed and questioned if innovative dissemination and Altmetrics should be focused on research content getting attention and getting viral. Another point raised was that qualitative assessment is completely lost with Altmetrics. Currently, there are no metrics that take into account the content of what is disseminated. This dimension could probably be included into Altmetrics, but this is not happening right now. In this context, it is important to foster a new movement towards holistic assessment of research impact. It is crucial to assess on what basis the metrics are used, what they can indicate, and which interpretations they allow for and which they don't. One of the main outcomes of the discussion was that more research needs to be done on the matter to get clearer answers to these questions.

Overall assessment of the workshop outcome

The results from both workshops give a good additional insight into current practices and perceived values of alternative dissemination channels and the use of Altmetrics. Also, we gained some additional input from non-practicing scientists, which is a useful complement to the survey results and the feedback from the first workshop. Since the daily work by researchers is to some extent influenced by decisions taken and rules established by policy makers, research funders, and publishers (e.g. incentives and rewards, requirements to get funding or to get tenure, established dissemination channels and available functionalities) this is an interesting perspective to include in further reasoning and implementation of the OpenUP objectives.